

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF SPEED OF PROFESSIONAL COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH STANDARDIZED EXERCISES

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Abstract: *This article discusses the running processes of girls who study at a vocational college. It helps how to speed up running processes, how to start, where to start, etc.*

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Running is one of the most accessible types of physical activity. Minimum equipment, maximum capabilities. You can run around the house in the park or square, at the stadium, on the treadmill at home or in the fitness club, along the embankment of the resort where you are resting. A variety of training modes: from the easiest run, to intensive intervals. This makes running an effective exercise for a person with any level of physical fitness. Clarity of movement coordination: everyone who can walk can run (with the exception of health contraindications, of course). So far, there are more men than women among running enthusiasts. But the interest of the beautiful half of humanity in this type of activity is growing every year.

Three key principles that will allow you to keep the desire to run

Regularity

The optimal amount of training for a beginner: 3-4 times a week - maximum. For example, running on Monday, Wednesday, Friday and/or Saturday. The rest of the days – rest or light exercises to strengthen the press (twisting the body and / or the bar) and legs (squats, lunges). This will allow the body to recover well physically and emotionally and tune in to a uniform rhythm of work and rest.

If the schedule of life is floating, then train following these principles: the break between workouts should be at least a day and no more than three; it is better to run twice every week than four times in one week, and then do nothing at all for two weeks.

Gradual increase in load

A lot of people started running and quit after two weeks. Most of them neglected the golden rule of all workouts: you need to start with a small load, which your body will perceive as joy, but not as stress and punishment.

Intensive walking is a good alternative to slow running, if it is still difficult for you. Or if you have a lot of excess weight (more than 10 extra kilograms).

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Remember that the wrong runner is cool, who immediately ran fast and a lot, and then did not go out for a second run because of muscle pain, shortness of breath and the shock state of the nervous system from such a "sport". The one who started small is cool. If you ran the last time at school / institute or if more than a month has passed since the last run, then start with walking workouts.

Walk one stop to the transport or leave the car a little further from the office and take a walk.

For the first week or two, just walk at an ordinary pace. It is better to do two walks of 10 minutes a day than to run a kilometer in 6 minutes in one run.

Then go to a faster step. With each workout, you can increase the distance covered by 100-200 meters. You will notice that such workouts are easy. There is no resistance to go outside just to take a walk.

If you are ready to run a little, then start alternating walking and slow running: run slowly for 1 minute (pulse up to 120-140 beats per minute).

Then walk actively for 3 minutes, helping yourself with your hands (the pulse should decrease to 100-110 beats).

Repeat this so many times to feel the warmth in the body, but not to experience severe discomfort.

This mode gives the heart, blood vessels and lungs a moderate load, protects the joints, does not overload the nerves – training takes place at an acceptable level of load.

The gradual increase in the load is important for the health of the immune system: the body needs to adapt to a new rhythm of work, because when we move at a higher speed than usual, all body systems need to adjust to a new regime. This is useful for the body only if the load increases smoothly and gradually. It is also necessary to do workouts regularly, as we have already written above. After long breaks, you will need to start from the beginning – with walking.

Then you can gradually increase the duration of running segments and shorten the duration of walking. If you practice regularly, you will feel progress: breathing will become easier, the body will adapt to the alternating speed of movement. You will want to increase the total duration of training. You can increase the total number of minutes by 10% every week.

If the word running gives you a feeling of heaviness, pain and suffering, then you are running too fast. Slow down or walk at a brisk pace at such a speed that the workout evokes a sense of joy.

With this approach, the issue of motivation to train will be automatically resolved. We all like to do what gives us pleasure.

A conscious plan

Think ahead and imagine:

What days of the week will you train? What can affect the postponement of training? It is best to add workouts to the calendar – so there is less risk of missing out because of other important things.

Where will you train? Outdoors or indoors? What kind of surface will you run on?

The answers to these questions will determine what equipment you will need to prepare for training.

For indoor classes (in college and other sports buildings), you need a light running uniform.

Conclusion: Running is available to almost everyone. Anyone who can walk can run. The only question is speed. Jogging will relieve stress, cheer up, switch from household chores or work force majeure. Running is called dynamic meditation. The body moves cyclically and if the pace of movement is comfortable, then such movement causes pleasure and even a state of light trance.

With sufficient readiness of the body, running can become a way to satisfy sports ambitions. You will be able to become part of a society of healthy, active people striving for development.

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